

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance to ufra disease in Burma

Tin Sein, Plant Pathology Department, Agricultural Research Institute, Rangoon, Burma

Ufra disease caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* will spread if normal and diseased rice plants are grown in the same paddy water. In three rainy seasons, 1972–74, seedlings of 151 varieties and 76 crosses were grown in 1-sq-m plots; when they were 1 month old, four to six diseased C4-63 plants were introduced into each plot. One month later the seedlings were transplanted to an isolated field. The percentage of fertile tillers at flowering time was recorded.

Sixty varieties and 12 crosses died, including C4-63, IR5, IR24, and many Burmese varieties common to the Irrawaddy Delta. More than 72% of the tillers of 8 varieties and 5 crosses flowered in one season but fewer in the other two seasons. Only the variety B-69-1 (Tha-baung-mee-gok), a selection from the indigenous rice of Tha-baung, a town in Irrawaddy Delta, showed more than 72% fertile tillers in all three seasons.

When 15 randomly selected hills each of diseased (inoculated) and of healthy B-69-1 rice were observed in 1974, the symptoms on diseased plants showed that B-69-1 is only tolerant. But the variety is useful, along with other control measures such as stubble-burning, clean cultivation, roguing, and flood control, for reducing the nematode population. ❧

Breakdown at low temperature of IR20 resistance to tungro virus

G. Mohana Rao and A. Anjaneyulu, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack-753006, India

A reselection of the cultivar IR20 has been found to be highly resistant in the field to the Cuttack isolate of the rice

tungro virus in kharif during the last 4 years. In monthly plantings for 2½ years, IR20 maintained its resistance during monsoon (July–October) and summer (March–June) seasons, but not during winter (November–February). Average maximum and minimum temperatures were 28.5 and 15.8°C during the 1974–75 winter season, and 28.6 and 15.2°C during the 1975–76 winter. Infected plants were a richer green than healthy plants, and were stunted during the summer and monsoon seasons. During winter, the

older leaves of infected plants were orange, while newly emerging leaves exhibited chlorosis. Infected plants were severely stunted, and showed symptoms more or less like those of susceptible TN1. Healthy plants in the same season had no discoloration. Symptom severity increased in December and January.

As many as 14.2% of the leafhoppers could become viruliferous during winter, as against 0.9% during summer and 2.1% during monsoon (average of 2 years).

Symptomatological polymorphism of a rice variety under differential climatic conditions may pose a problem, especially in identification of strains of rice tungro virus at several sites of the International Rice Tungro Nursery. ❧

Insect resistance

Rice varieties and the white-tip nematode

G. Rajendran, T. S. Muthukrishnan, and M. Balasubramanian, Department of Agricultural Entomology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore-3, India

Rice yield losses of up to 60% are attributable to the rice white-tip caused by the nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi*

The white-tip nematode causes rice yield loss of up to 60% in Tamil Nadu, India.

in the State of Tamil Nadu, India. One hundred and one rice cultivars were screened under natural conditions in the field from July 1973 to July 1976. The number of chaffy spikelets per panicle was recorded as an indication of nematode damage. Entries with less than 5% infestation and other selected entries are shown in the table. ❧

Rice panicle infestation by white-tip nematode. Tamil Nadu, India, 1973–76.

Rice cultivar	Chaffy spikelets (%/panicle)
Co 13	1
Rohini	1
T 292	1
RP 113-31	1
Ratna	2
T 228	2
Triveni	2
TKM 7	2
T 482	2
ASD 14	2
Yamuna	2
Padma	2
IR5	2
SR 26B	3
Cul-7711	3
Vijaya	3
Sona	3
Soorya	3
IR30	3
Krishna	4
Bala	4
CR 12-178	4
IR8	12
IR26	14
TN1	30
GEB 24	50
TKM 6	55